

Employment Scenario of People with Disability in India

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Abstract

Activists assert that despite recent increases in the percentage of handicapped workers in sectors like finance, progress in ensuring that disabled individuals may find employment in India is painfully slow and that statutory targets are required to compel private enterprises to engage more impaired talent. Despite legislation encouraging diversity in the workplace, people with disabilities still do not have the same access to employment opportunities as individuals without impairments. One billion, or 15%, of the world's population, are thought to have impairments. 80 percent of the population is working age. But it's common for people with disabilities to be denied their right to respectable employment. There are significant psychological, physical, and informational hurdles that prevent people with disabilities, especially women, from enjoying equal chances in the workplace.

Keywords: Disability, Person with Disability, PwD, employment, impaired

Introduction

"*Nihil de nobis, sine nobis*" (Latin for "Nothing about us, without us") has served as the rallying cry of the disability movement all around the world. Since it represented the first time in independent India's history that a comprehensive strategy to enhance the rights, participation, and equality of people with disabilities was formulated, the Disability Act, 1995, was viewed as a significant development (Khazanachi et al., 2022). Males made up 78% of the working population with disabilities in 2019. Women with disabilities have a higher unemployment rate (Bandyopadhyay, 2022). Despite this vast resource pool, the topic of employment for those with disabilities has received very little attention from stakeholders. Although certain opportunities have opened up since The Disability Act was passed in 1995, particularly in the fields of education and work, there is still a long way to go before the nation or society views people with disabilities as valuable human resources (Jindal and Chari, 2006).

Despite the implementation of the "The People with Disabilities" Act, which reserves 3% of all categories of jobs in the government sector for disabled people, the needs of disabled people for meaningful employment continue to go unmet, despite the fact that they make up a sizable 5 to 6% of India's population. One billion, or 15%, of the world's population, are thought to have impairments. 80 percent of the population is working age. But it's common for people with disabilities to be denied their right to respectable employment. There are

significant psychological, physical, and informational hurdles that prevent people with disabilities, especially women, from enjoying equal chances in the workplace (Bonaccio et al., 2009).

PWDs in Workplaces

PWDs are neglected and vulnerable in today's world due to their limited abilities and the difficulties they face in almost every aspect of life. PWDs are less likely to be hired and keep a job than non-disabled people. Disabled people face discrimination and violations of their human rights in the workplace, and they are frequently mistreated in society. They may be subjected to physical, emotional, or sexual abuse, and their rights to make personal and financial decisions for themselves are denied (Naraharisetti and Castro, 2016). The Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights, and Full Participation Act, 1995, and the National Policy for Persons with Disabilities, ratified in 2006, are the two major initiatives taken by the Government of India for the welfare of PWDs. The PWD Act of 1995 required quotas in education and public services, as well as making buildings and facilities accessible. This law was revised in 2016, with the reservation quota increased from 3% to 4%. To ensure that these vacancies are filled with PWDs under the 4% quota, the government of India has schemes such as relaxation of upper age limit, training and welfare, regulation of employment, health and safety measures.

Figure 1. Representation of total number of disabled people (approximate) all over India

The above figure was constructed using Excel that indicates the number of disabled people (approximately) all over India after going through the cited review papers (Naraharisetti and Castro, 2016).

Benefits of Hiring PWDs

Although employers believe that people with disabilities are less productive in the workplace, studies show that people with disabilities are more dedicated, reliable, and punctual than their non-disabled counterparts. Hiring PWDs can boost the company's productivity and profit margins because they are more loyal, punctual, and conscientious. PWDs gain satisfaction from their jobs and feel obligated that their employers have invested in them and trained them to be employable, which increases profitability (Gooding and Marriot, 2020).

Figure 2. Reasons as to why organizations want to hire PwDs

The above illustration has been taken from (Gooding and Marriot, 2020) and gives a detailed view of why there's a benefit of hiring PwDs.

Barriers Faced by PWDs

Some of the difficulties encountered in successfully employing PWDs include: a lack of education and training; a lack of adequate resources; a lack of awareness in employers regarding the difficulties faced by PWDs; a lack of positive attitudes toward PWDs; the social stigma that PWDs cannot obtain meaningful employment; a lack of proper infrastructure to accommodate the needs of PWDs; poor accessibility; workplace discrimination and harassment; low literacy rates in PWDs; and an unwillingness to hire PWDs. Frequently, the job requirements posted by the employer do not match the skill set of PWDs. PWDs are not adequately prepared for written tests and job interviews by vocational training centres. Furthermore, many non-governmental organisations (NGOs) lack training facilities for preparing PWDs for employment in the current labour market. Weak enforcement of laws, the employment quota being restricted to the public sector, and not including all disabilities in the quota all make it difficult for PWDs to find work (Arun Kumar et al., 2012).

Figure 3. The various disabilities among PwDs

The above illustration (Bandyopadhyay, 2022) summarizes the various disabilities among the PwDs. Physical disability is most predominant and is closely followed by locomotor disability.

Legal Framework for PWDs

On February 7, 1996, "The Persons with Disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) Act, 1995" went into effect. It is a critical step that guarantees the inclusion of individuals with disabilities in all aspects of nation-building and provides them with equal chances. The Act covers both preventive and promotional aspects of rehabilitation, such as education, employment and vocational training,

reservations, research and manpower development, the creation of barrier-free environments, the rehabilitation of people with disabilities, unemployment benefits for people with disabilities, a special insurance programme for people with disabilities working, the establishment of homes for people with severe disabilities, etc (Yildiz et al., 2010). The Proclamation on the Full Participation and Equality of People with Disabilities in the Asian and Pacific Region, which India adopted in December 1992, required India to implement the PWD Act, which went into effect on January 1st, 1996. The Act includes a number of provisions for people with disabilities to make it easier for them to access social assistance programmes, basic infrastructure, work opportunities, education, and other services (Arun Kumar et al., 2012).

According to the PWD Act, a "person with disability" is someone who has 40% or more of one of the following impairments: Blindness, low vision, leprosy cure, hearing impairment, locomotor disability, mental retardation, and mental disease are only a few examples of disabilities. This is a constrained definition, since only individuals who meet the criteria of having 40% or more of the aforementioned 7 disabilities would be considered individuals with disabilities and be eligible to benefit from the rights and programmes provided by the PWD Act. The primary rights that are available to people with disabilities include those related to education in public schools, public employment, infrastructure on the roads and in public transportation, and access to public buildings, as well as a grievance system for the preservation of their rights (Jindal and Chari, 2006).

PWDs in Public Sector

In most countries, the public sector is the largest employer. However, the picture changes when it comes to hiring disabled people. The private sector has a higher rate of protective jobs than the public sector. A few studies on the subject exist, and they show that administrators of employment support programmes for disabled people have neglected the public sector. The reasons for this situation differ from one state to the next. To begin with, the public sector has been shrinking in most countries, and the majority of public employees have either retired or been displaced (Bonaccio et al., 2009). The public sector, which offers full-time employment and job differentiation, as well as all-purpose benefits, has seen a significant number of employees retire or be displaced. Disability allowances are one of the factors that have contributed to the increased prominence of the disabled employment issue in recent years. As a result, if public sector employment for disabled people is created through an appropriate environment and a well-designed support programme, fees and financial supports do not exceed the national average of amounts spent on employment supports, and disabled people's income approaches the national average (Yildiz et al., 2010).

One of the most significant contributions of the Disability Act 1995 in India was the creation of job opportunities in Grade A and Grade B positions. Prior to the Act's passage, only jobs of Grade C and D were available to people with disabilities. According to some estimates, there are more than 15,000 reserved job vacancies in the government and public sector for people with disabilities that have yet to be filled. The "identification of jobs" remains a major concern. Many jobs are still "unidentified" for people with disabilities. As a result of this discriminatory policy, many qualified people with disabilities are denied jobs in the government. All jobs should be detailed in terms of the skills required and the essential functions of the job. Many countries around the world have adopted the practice, which not only assists people with disabilities but also non-disabled people in making career decisions.

Figure 4. Inclusion of Disabled people in workplace

The figure, taken from (Uddin, 2022), gives a view of the employment scenario of the disabled in India. The graph denoted a much positive view and shows inclusion of the disabled people in the various job sectors.

PWDs in Private Sector

Many initiatives have been launched by various stakeholders to support the employment of people with disabilities in India to date (from Govt. as well as from private organizations). Aside from government initiatives, private employers, public-private partnership firms, and prominent nongovernmental organizations collaborate with their respective associations to create PwD employment. APD, Enable India, National Center for Promotion of Employment of Disabled People (NCPEDP), Able disabled all people together (ADAPT) Mumbai, Ability foundation, Chennai, Enable India, Bangalore, and a few others are among them (Ramachandra et al., 2017). In the last two decades or so, employment in the private sector has grown at an increasing rate. However, the representation of people with disabilities in the private sector workforce is very low. The private sector was only mentioned in Clause 41 of The Disability Act, which required the government to announce incentives to promote employment of people with disabilities in both the public and private sectors (Ramachandra et al., 2017).

The private sector has been actively hiring people with disabilities for the past decade or so. It is certainly far from the ideal state of equal participation of people with disabilities in the sector. Certain service industries, such as information technology (IT), retail, and hospitality, have been proactive in hiring a fairly large group of individuals with disabilities (Kitching and Arzeni, 2014). Few major corporations, such as Wipro, Mphasis, and IBM, hire people from various disability groups to perform a variety of jobs. Organizations such as EMC and SAP offer internship opportunities to people with high support needs, such as those with autism, deaf-blindness, multiple disabilities, and so on. Companies like Lemon Tree and JW Marriott have hired people with various disabilities, including those with intellectual disabilities. Companies such as Sun-ITES, Lemon Tree Hotels, and Vindhya e-infomedia distinguish themselves as having a sizable (10%+) workforce of people with disabilities (Uddin, 2022).

Figure 5. Representation of employment status of PwD in the private sector

The above pie chart was constructed using Excel to show the employment status of the PwDs.

Self Employment scenario of Disabled people

Self-employment rates vary by type and severity of impairment, gender, education, and residential location, according to the personal characteristics of disabled entrepreneurs. People who were severely limited in their daily activities reported higher rates of self-employment than those who reported some or no limitation in daily activities (Lindsay et al., 2017). Studies illustrate either the influence of 'pull' factors such as independence/autonomy and material benefits or the influence of 'push' factors such as unemployment or employer discrimination, despite the fact that individual choices to become self-employed are necessarily influenced by the larger socioeconomic context. Self-employment may provide disabled people with the

flexibility in work tasks, pacing, hours, and location that they seek, as well as a better adjustment between disability status and working life (Kitching and Arzeni, 2014).

The National Handicapped Finance and Development Corporation (NHFDC) offers low-interest loans to people with disabilities. In the fiscal year 2011-12, the total number of beneficiaries was 10,625 and the total amount disbursed was Rs. 50.86 crores. In the last five years or so, there has been a tremendous increase in entrepreneurship initiatives in the country, particularly in technology-based start-ups. Unfortunately, people with disabilities appear to be missing out in this area as well. No prominent entrepreneur with a disability has ever been funded. Second, while many of the products and services offered by these start-ups can be extremely beneficial and enabling for people with disabilities, they are still inaccessible to the vast majority of people with disabilities (Ramachandra et al., 2017).

Figure 6: Self Employment scenario of Disabled people

This graph gives an insight of how many disabled people are sitting at home or working in various sectors. Taken from (Lindsay et al., 2017), Physicist Stephen Hawking claims that it is our moral obligation to remove obstacles that prevent persons with disabilities from participating in society and to provide them with the resources and knowledge necessary to realise their full potential. Disability increases a person's vulnerability to poverty and unemployment (Arun Kumar et al., 2012).

Case study

This case study looks into the difficulties that people with intellectual impairments encounter in Bangladesh while trying to find and keep inclusive jobs, and it also identifies best practices for creating inclusive workplaces. Twenty people, including those with intellectual disabilities, family members, and employers, were interviewed in Bangladesh. People with intellectual disabilities described a variety of obstacles, such as bullying and harassment at work, discrimination in hiring procedures, substantial underpayment (in some circumstances, 25% of the wage of someone doing the same job, and in other situations, 50% of the national minimum wage) (Ebuenyi et al., 2019). Family members named bullying and harassment, prejudice, a lack of inclusive education, and accessibility transportation as major hindrances. Employers cited prejudice from coworkers, a lack of awareness of intellectual disability, and concerns about acceptable accommodations as the main impediments.

Figure 7. People with Down syndrome in Bangladesh

People with intellectual disabilities are more likely to not live an independent life due to obstacles such as exclusion from social and economic activities, stigma, prejudice, ignorance, neglect, and social and attitudinal hurdles. Individuals in Bangladesh who have intellectual disability deal with a variety of discrimination when taking part in initiatives for national development (Kitching and Arzeni, 2014). The Bangladeshi government, NGOs, and organizations for people with disabilities (OPDs) are making an effort to incorporate people with intellectual disabilities in both the formal and informal job sectors, nevertheless. The goal of this case study is to pinpoint the most effective methods for employing people with intellectual disability in Bangladesh (Ebuenyi et al., 2019).

Issues with the Case Study

Most respondents could not be met in person to conduct face-to-face interviews because of COVID-19 constraints. Finding effective methods was especially difficult because Bangladesh now employs very few people with intellectual disability. Some NGOs have started the process of hiring people with intellectual disability, setting a great example for other companies.

Conclusion

PWDs are an important resource in our society, and their existence should not be overlooked. We must respect and accept them for who they are. PWDs can improve company image and profit by fostering an inclusive work culture and increasing ability awareness. Finding meaningful work will improve one's quality of life, self-confidence, social network, and sense of belonging while also providing a source of income. PWDs can become productive members of society and lead a quality life if they have equal employment opportunities, adequate training, accommodations, an accessible workplace, and mandates that are properly enforced.

References

1. *Current Scenario of Employment of Person with Disabilities in India*, Rashmi Khazanchi, Vinita Mehta, Pankaj Khazanchi
2. *Disabled workers in India: lifting the barriers* |. (2022, August 5). <https://www.britsafe.in/publications-and-blogs/safety-management-magazine/safety-management-magazine/2022/disabled-workers-in-india-lifting-the-barriers/>
3. *Employment Scenario of People with Disabilities in India*, Ankit Rajiv Jindal and Rama Chari Diversity and Equal Opportunity Centre (DEOC)
4. Bonaccio, S., Connelly, C.E., Gellatly, I.R. et al. The Participation of People with Disabilities in the Workplace Across the Employment Cycle: Employer Concerns and Research Evidence. *J Bus Psychol*
5. Campbell, Shawn, and Lisa Dunne. "Disability and Work." [www.ilo.org](http://www.ilo.org/global/topics/disability-and-work/lang--en/index.htm), 5 Apr. 2009, www.ilo.org/global/topics/disability-and-work/lang--en/index.htm.
6. *Factors associated with persons with disability employment in India: a cross-sectional study* by Ramya Naraharisetti & Marcia C. Castro

7. *The Participation of People with Disabilities in the Workplace Across the Employment Cycle: Employer Concerns and Research Evidence* by Silvia Bonaccio, Catherine E. Connelly, Ian R. Gellatly, Arif Jetha & Kathleen A. Martin Ginis
8. *Analysis of disabled employment in the Public sector*, İshak ÇİFTÇİ et. all, 2015
9. Kitching, John. (2014). *Entrepreneurship and self-employment by people with disabilities*.
10. *Current State of Inclusion of People with Disabilities at Workplaces in India*, Devpriya
11. *Including persons with disabilities in social cash transfer programmes in developing countries*, Kate Gooding, Anna Marriot
12. Piramanayagam, Senthilkumaran and Seal, Partho Pratim, *Employers' Attitudes and Hiring Intentions towards Persons with Disabilities in Hotels in India* (February 14, 2021). Disability, CBR and Inclusive Development 2020,
13. *When affirmative action is not enough: challenges in career development of persons with disability*, Amit Gupta Pushendra Priyadarshi
14. *Trapped Between Ableism And Neoliberalism: Critical Reflections On Disability And Employment In India*, Kumar, Arun and Sonpal, Deepa and Hiranandani, Vanmala (2012)
15. *PERSONS WITH DISABILITY & THE INDIA LABOUR MARKET: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES*, Meera Shenoy December 2011
16. *Impact sourcing for employment of persons with disabilities*. Katsuo Matsumoto, [Social Enterprise Journal](#)
17. Ramachandra SS, Murthy GVS, Shamanna BR, Allagh KP, Pant HB, John N. *Factors Influencing Employment and Employability for Persons with Disability: Insights from a City in South India*. *Indian J Occup Environ Med*. 2017
18. Gupta, Bhawna & Arora, Rimpi. (2020). *Rights and Entitlements of Persons with Disabilities in India: An Evaluation*.
19. Uddin, Md Taslim . “Disability-Inclusive Employment.” *New Age | the Most Popular Outspoken English Daily in Bangladesh*, 7 May 2022
20. Ebuenyi, Ikenna D., et al. “Expectations Management; Employer Perspectives on Opportunities for Improved Employment of Persons with Mental Disabilities in Kenya*.” *Disability and Rehabilitation*, vol. 42, no. 12, 7 Jan. 2019, pp. 1687–1696, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2018.1534006>. Accessed 27 June 2021.
21. Strindlund, Lena, et al. “Employers’ Views on Disability, Employability, and Labor Market Inclusion: A Phenomenographic Study.” *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 30 June 2018, pp. 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2018.1481150>. Accessed 21 Aug. 2019.
22. Kwan, Chi Kin. “Helping People with Disabilities in the Workplace: Mezzo-Level Interventions Targeting Corporate Culture.” *Social Work*, 30 July 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1093/sw/swab030>.
23. Lindsay, Sally, et al. “A Systematic Review of Workplace Disclosure and Accommodation Requests among Youth and Young Adults with Disabilities.” *Disability and Rehabilitation*, vol. 40, no. 25, 10 Aug. 2017, pp. 2971–2986, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2017.1363824>.